

A Review of Technical Aspects and Challenges in Opportunistic Rainfall Estimation Using Satellite and Terrestrial Microwave Links

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Abstract—The idea of using terrestrial or satellite microwave links as opportunistic sensors (OSs) of rainfall is more than 15 years old and the literature on the topic is vast. Many studies focused on rain detection and quantification from the data collected by the front- and back-hauling links of mobile networks, namely, commercial microwave links (CMLs). More recently, several researchers have also investigated the signals received by the ground terminals of TV-SAT or of IoT satellite-based service subscribers, namely satellite microwave links (SMLs). CMLs and SMLs have different characteristics than conventional sensors (CSs) of rainfall, hence they have the potential to complement measurements collected by rain gauges (RGs) or weather radars (WRs), as well as to provide unique data in the several areas of the globe where rainfall monitoring systems are scarce or missing at all. Unlike previous reviews on the topic, this work aims at surveying the technical challenges involved by the usage of devices and data not designed for rainfall monitoring. In particular, we draw a state-of-the-art flowchart of OS data processing, we analyze the disturbances that affect the raw data, and, finally, we present a comparative analysis of the major studies on the validation of OS rainfall estimates, based on a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The similarities and differences of satellite and terrestrial links as rainfall sensors are highlighted. To conclude, we propose an author’s view on the future of rainfall measurements by CMLs and SMLs, which is closely tied to the evolution of wireless communication networks.

Index Terms—Rain retrieval, rain fading, microwave propagation, opportunistic microwave sensing, microwave links, satellite communication downlinks.

ACRONYMS

AI Artificial Intelligence

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ANN Artificial Neural Network
 ATPC Automatic Transmit Power Control
 CCDF Complementary Cumulative Distribution Function
 CML Commercial Microwave Link
 CNN Convolutional Neural Network
 COTS Commercially available Off-The-Shelf
 CS Conventional Sensor
 CV Coefficient of Variation
 DSD Drop Size Distribution
 DTH Direct-To-Home
 DVB-S/S2 Digital Video Broadcasting - Satellite/Satellite 2nd generation
 FT Fast Tracker
 GEO Geostationary Earth Orbit
 HM Harmonic Mean
 IF Intermediate-Frequency
 IPL Ice Particle Layer
 KPI Key Performance Indicator
 LEO Low-Earth Orbit
 LL Liquid Layer
 LNB Low-Noise Block
 LSTM Long Short Term Memory
 LWC Liquid Water Content
 MBE Mean Bias Error
 MCC Matthews Correlation Coefficient
 MDE Mean Detection Error
 ML Melting Layer
 MNO Mobile Network Operator
 NMAE Normalized Mean Absolute Error
 NRMSE Normalized bias-corrected Root Mean Square Error
 OS Opportunistic Sensor
 PCC Pearson Correlation Coefficient
 PSD Particle Size Distribution
 RB Relative Bias
 RF Radio-Frequency
 RG Rain Gauge
 RMSE Root Mean Square Error
 RMSE_r Root Mean Square of relative Error
 RSL Received Signal Level
 SML Satellite Microwave Link
 SNR Signal-to-Noise Ratio
 ST Slow Tracker
 SVM Support Vector Machine
 TBRG Tipping-Bucket Rain Gauge
 TSL Transmitted Signal Level

WAA Wet Antenna Attenuation

WR Weather Radar

I. INTRODUCTION

QUANTITATIVE precipitation estimation is crucial for a broad spectrum of applications including meteorology [1], climatology [2], weather forecasting [3], hydrology [4] and water management [5]. Nowadays, networks of Rain Gauges (RGs) [6] and Weather Radars (WRs) [7], [8] are the key instruments for measuring precipitation at operational level. Additionally, Earth observation satellites provide precipitation products over large areas [9], even though with a lower spatial and temporal resolution. Furthermore, disdrometers are increasingly used as they are able to measure the size and velocity of falling raindrops [10]. Several applications require small scale measurements and fast sampling [11] to track localized and rapidly evolving severe rainfall events, which are more and more frequent, as an effect of climate change. The required resolution of rainfall measurements can be in the order of 10 km, down to 100 m, in space, and 10 min, down to 1 min, in time. Current operational networks of rain sensors can not provide the above performance everywhere.

In addition to the above instruments, referred to as Conventional Sensors (CSs), new opportunities are opening up thanks to the growth of wireless telecommunication networks worldwide. Indeed, any terrestrial or satellite-to-ground link operating at a frequency that is sensitive to rainfall (roughly, above 5 GHz) is, in principle, an Opportunistic Sensor (OS) of precipitation, provided that the time series of the Received Signal Level (RSL) are collected and stored by the system. The RSL can be either the received power or some equivalent quantity such as the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). Examples are the back-hauling links of terrestrial cellular networks, hereinafter named Commercial Microwave Links (CMLs) or the downlinks of Direct-To-Home (DTH) satellite broadcasting, namely Satellite Microwave Links (SMLs). A schematic overview of the main technical characteristics of CS and OS sensors is shown in Table I, in order to highlight the main differences in terms of frequency range, collected variables, spatial and temporal resolutions, and economic costs.

Opportunistic sensing of precipitation through CMLs and SMLs has several advantages:

- In many low-income countries, networks of WRs are not available and RGs are scarce [12], due to their high installation and maintenance costs. In addition, providing free access to these data is challenging [13]. On the other hand, the ubiquitous growth of wireless communications turned OSs into a solution for the quick deployment of rain sensing networks in these countries [14]–[17];
- Where RGs or WRs are already in place, OSs represent an efficient and low-cost solution to complement the operational networks of CSs, filling gaps or improving coverage [18]. Moreover, merging OS and CS data or different types of OS data can significantly improve the accuracy of rainfall estimates [19], [20].
- CML and SML microwave receivers are able to collect rainfall data with a fine temporal resolution, that is, in

the order of 1-min [21]–[24]. Moreover, precipitation is observed by OSs along a straight line corresponding to the propagation path of the electromagnetic wave [25], [26]. The combination of high resolution in time and spatial sampling capability as well as the availability of dense networks of sensors (in the case of CMLs) results in a more effective measurement of the spatial distribution of rainfall intensity than in the case of RGs [18].

In the following Sections I-A and I-B, CSs and OSs are briefly reviewed, while Section I-C summarizes the major contributions of this review.

A. Conventional sensors

Ground-based RGs such as the plain old Tipping-Bucket Rain Gauge (TBRG) or the more advanced Weighing-Type Gauge (WTG) are relatively simple sensors and are currently the primary reference for rainfall measurements [6]. Standards for the accuracy of RG measurements are provided by the recommendations of the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) [27]. RGs are point-based devices with a small capture area (i.e., usually less than 1000 cm²), which is a major limitation when evaluating the spatial variability of rainfall is important. Moreover, TBRGs are known to underestimate at heavy rainfall intensities [28] or in the presence of wind [29].

Disdrometers are another type of point-sensors [10], [30], [31]. They are able to measure the microphysical properties of precipitation, such as the Particle Size Distribution (PSD), which is important for several applications. It is known that disdrometers may undercount small drops with diameters smaller than about 0.3 mm [10]. In addition, disdrometer measurements are affected by the presence of wind, which results in a bias of the measured PSD [32], [33].

Ground-based WRs provide a broad spatial coverage, i.e., up to 150 km, as well as high spatial and temporal resolutions, i.e. in the order of 1 km in space and 5-10 in time, respectively [7]. However, they provide indirect measurements of precipitation [34] collected aloft rather than at ground, and they are not immune to measurement errors (e.g., miscalibration or attenuation effects). As a result, the capability of WRs to provide quantitative precipitation estimates remains an issue [34]. Furthermore, the coverage of ground-based radar can be limited in regions with complex orography [35]. WRs on board satellites provide regional coverage and contribute to the understanding of large-scale precipitation processes. On the other hand, they have a much lower temporal resolution and a lower spatial resolution than ground-based radars [8]. For instance, the Dual-Frequency Precipitation radar on board the Global Precipitation Measurement [36] core LEO satellite, has a 5 km × 5 km footprint and a revisit time of about 4 times per month. A higher temporal resolution is provided by the Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) product that combines data from the different sensors on board the Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM) satellite constellation [37]. Satellite products are obtained through complex algorithms and need continuous validation processes [38].

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF THE KEY FEATURES OF CSS AND OSS.

Sensor	CS			OS	
	Weather Radar	Rain Gauge	Disdrometer	CML	SML
Frequency range	2 – 10 GHz ^a	-	Infrared or visible	6 – 42 GHz ^b 71 – 76 GHz ^d 81 – 86 GHz ^d	10.70 – 12.75 GHz ^c 17.70 – 21.20 GHz ^c
Measured variables	- Reflectivity - Doppler velocity - Polarimetric variables	Cumulated rain	- Particle fall velocity - Particle size	Path attenuation	
Primary geophysical variables	- Precipitation intensity - Hydrometeor classification	Cumulated rain	- Particle size distribution - Precipitation intensity - Precipitation type	Precipitation intensity	
Spatial sampling	Over volumes	Point-based sensor		Over a straight line (terrestrial path)	Over a straight line (space-to-Earth path)
Spatial resolution (single sensor)	1 × 1 km ^f	N/A		N/A ^g	
Spatial resolution (networks of sensors)	1 × 1 km	Average distance between sensors			
Temporal resolution	5 – 10 min	1 – 30 min	1 min (typical)	10 s–15 min	30 s – 15 min
Cost (single sensor)^h	€ 150 k – 1 M (X-band) ^a € 1.5 M – 3.5 M (C-band) ^a € 3 M – 8 M (S-band) ^a	€ 100 – 2 k	€ 3 k – 70 k	Upon agreement with MNO	€ 100 – 1 k

^a Most widely used weather radar bands S-band (2.7 – 2.9 GHz), C-band (5.250 – 5.725 GHz) and X-band (9.3 – 9.5 GHz)

^b Non-continuous allocations. This frequency range encompasses several microwave and mmWave bands from C-band to Q-band.

^c K_n-band

^d E-band

^e K_a-band

^f Weather radar products are typically 2D maps of rainfall intensity at ground.

^g CMLs and SMLs are often considered as point-based sensors located for instance midway through the path or at the ground terminal of an SML.

^h Installation, maintenance, and operational costs are excluded here because they depend on many different variables. For CMLs, the cost is relative to the data, which is subject to an agreement with the MNO.

B. Opportunistic sensors

Wireless terrestrial links and Earth-satellite links operating in the microwave range of frequencies can be used as OSs of precipitation. The physical background is the same. Both rely on the decrease of the RSL while it is raining along the link, due to the absorption and scattering of the electromagnetic wave by the raindrops and referred to as rain attenuation [39]. Rain attenuation is directly related to the rainfall intensity along the propagation path. However, there are significant differences between CMLs and SMLs, including: *i*) the frequency bands allocated for satellite and terrestrial services (listed in Table I), *ii*) the way raw data useful to precipitation estimation are generated and made available, *iii*) the way raw data are processed to derive precipitation estimates, and *iv*) the sources of disturbances affecting the RSL, which may impact the accuracy of precipitation estimates.

1) CMLs

The acronym CML indicates the wireless line-of-sight point-to-point terrestrial links that provide back-hauling connectivity in mobile networks, i.e. the bridge between the radio access portion and the core of the network. Back-hauling links transmit across licensed bandwidths in the range of frequency 6–42 GHz [40] over path lengths from a few hundreds of meters to a few tens of kilometers. Recently, very short E-band links (71–86 GHz) have been installed especially in densely populated areas to support the increasing demand for high-capacity connectivity [41]. CMLs are designed to ensure extremely high link availability levels, typically in the order of 99.99% of the yearly time or even higher. To this aim,

both the RSL and the Transmitted Signal Level (TSL) by each link transceiver are continuously monitored. Rainfall intensity along the CML path can be retrieved from the raw data, i.e. the TSL and the RSL and from the metadata. The metadata set includes (at least) geographical position of the transceivers, frequency and polarization of the signals. An important issue regarding CMLs is that Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), that is, usually private companies, are the owners of the raw data. Moreover, the metadata are often classified as confidential, hence they can be accessed only after signing non-disclosure agreements. Indeed, communication with MNOs and potential users such as meteorological agencies and the development of sustainable business plans are fundamental aspects to promote the exploitation of CML data [42].

2) SMLs

The term SML refers to (at least) two different schemes based on Earth-space links, where the space terminal is usually a Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO) satellite. One scheme relies on the signals conveying classical broadcasting services delivered by satellite operators, such as Digital Video Broadcasting - Satellite/Satellite 2nd generation (DVB-S/S2) for TV-SAT. These signals can be measured installing low-cost receivers [43], wherever the data collected by a network of such devices need to be transferred to a server for processing. Differently from CML raw data, in this case the opportunistic data are generated (hence owned) by anybody able to install the receiving systems.

A different SML scheme is based on two-way Earth-space links such as the ones for satellite-based IoT services or Internet via satellite [44]. The received power or the SNR

measured by the ground receivers of the service subscribers are transmitted back to the gateway through the satellite, for instance, for link monitoring and data rate optimization. This scheme is similar as the one of CMLs, since data are generated within the operational framework of the network and they are managed by the satellite operator.

C. Outline of this work

This paper reviews the technical aspects involved in the use of CMLs and SMLs as OSs of rainfall. Other important aspects such as access to OS data and their availability for operational usage [22], standardization of data formats [45] and evolution of wireless networks are beyond the scope of this contribution, hence they are not investigated in depth here.

There are a few surveys in the literature on the topic of CMLs and SMLs. Some of them are rather general and touch on all the above aspects [42], [46], while others are limited to either CMLs [47] or SMLs [26]. Different from previous reviews, this work emphasizes signal impairments, physical limitations, and processing methodologies, filling the following gaps:

- it presents a general framework for OS data processing, highlighting the similarities and the differences between CML and SML data (Section II);
- it provides a comparative analysis of the major works on rainfall identification and quantification by CMLs and SMLs (Section IV).

This paper has three specific objectives, which are addressed in Sections II, III and IV, respectively:

- giving an overview of the methods for converting CML and SML raw data into rainfall estimates;
- discussing the disturbances that affect precipitation estimates obtained by CMLs and SMLs as well as their intrinsic limitations when used as precipitation sensors;
- proposing a rationale as well as a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to compare the performance of CML and SML data against the ones of CSs.

Conclusions and future trends are drawn in Section V. The ultimate goal of this review is to provide some recommendations and best practices, based on the current state of the art in the research, for the usage of OS data gathered from microwave links in the field of rainfall observation.

II. METHODOLOGY FOR RAINFALL RETRIEVAL FROM OS DATA

Methods for converting OS raw data into precipitation estimates (i.e., rainfall rate and rainfall accumulation) have been described in several papers in the literature (see e.g., [48], [24] for CML, or [49], [50] for SML). Moreover, there are a few open software tools available for processing CML data such as RAINLINK [51] or pycomlink [52]. Building from the research findings, we present a general framework for OS data processing, discussing the basic steps and highlighting the similarities and the differences between CMLs and SMLs.

The flowchart sketched in Fig. 1 shows a general processing chain for retrieving rainfall intensity from CML or SML

raw data. Hereafter, we briefly illustrate each block in the flowchart, wherein the alphanumeric labels of the block refer to the numbering of the corresponding descriptive subsections in the remainder of this section.

Fig. 1. General flowchart for processing rainfall estimates from microwave link data (either CMLs or SMLs).

A. RSL Measurement and Sampling

The receiver collects the RSL, i.e. the raw data, which consist of time series of the received power or of the SNR. The latter is defined as $\eta = E_s/N_0$, where E_s is the energy of the received Radio-Frequency (RF) signal (averaged over the duration of one digital modulation symbol) and N_0 is the one-sided power spectral density of the additive channel noise. RSL measurements are carried out within a given bandwidth at RF or at Intermediate-Frequency (IF) after down-conversion, and sampled at a specified rate. Moreover, depending on the practical implementation of the receiver, RSL can be either measured in analog form and subsequently digitized at a given sampling rate, or it can be obtained right in the digital domain using some signal processing algorithm applied to the samples of the received signal. In addition, the TSL (not shown in the figure) is often collected and made available in the case of CML. The two circular marks labeled CML and SML in Fig. 1 indicate the starting points of the data processing flow for terrestrial and for satellite links, respectively, where the word “processing” means the conversion process of the raw data into precipitation estimates. There are important differences between the format and the properties of CML and SML raw data, as outlined hereafter.

1) CMLs

The transmitters and the receivers of CMLs are part of the MNO infrastructure. RSL (and TSL) measurements are usually logged for link quality monitoring and maintenance purposes. They can be accessed only upon authorization of the MNO. Moreover, given the huge amount of links operating in large terrestrial networks, routinely transmitting these data

to a central server may pose issues. As a result: a) the data available from CML networks are not optimized for precipitation estimation, and b) the format and the sampling time of RSL and TSL are parameters out of user control, being constrained by the data acquisition method chosen by each MNO. A MINMAX data format is adopted in several cases, that is, the minimum and maximum RSL and TSL values over a fixed observation window are logged. The size of the window is typically 15-min [53] [54]. In other cases, nearly-instantaneous values collected every 1 min or even shorter intervals are available [42].

In summary, in the case of CMLs, the tasks associated with the light-gray block in Fig. 1 labeled “RSL Measurement & Sampling” are carried out by the MNO. The output sequence of RSL samples is made available by the MNO as “raw data” for precipitation studies.

2) SMLs

Satellite broadcast signals can be received anywhere within the satellite footprint and, differently from the CML case, there are no data ownership issues. In particular, the RSL can be collected without any intellectual property or copyright infringement, any authorization from the broadcaster or the satellite operator, or any fee to be paid. Any Commercially available Off-The-Shelf (COTS) terminal for DTH satellite services carries out real-time RSL measurements for different purposes (e.g. installation, monitoring, maintenance, etc.). However, the vast majority of COTS receivers do not support data logging. Therefore, RSL retrieval may entail some software or hardware modification of the device. This is not a straightforward task due to the lack of technical documentation from the manufacturers or to intellectual property restrictions. Furthermore, some communication technology, either wired (Ethernet or ADSL) or wireless (Wi-Fi or 4/5G network), is necessary for transferring RSL data to the servers of a remote processing centre.

One of the very few COTS satellite receivers allowing RSL retrieval is an innovative compact two-way device named SmartLNB [44], [55], which includes both an integrated DVB-S/S2 receiver and a transmitter for the return link (i.e., the ground-to-satellite link). The latter, besides user-generated contents for interactive TV services and local sensor data, also carries information about the status of the device, including high-rate readings (1 or 2 samples per minute) of the SNR. These data are then up-linked to the satellite, which, in turn, relays them down to the processing center. This solution is simple and effective, but it requires a subscription fee for each SmartLNB and the availability of a return link. As an alternative to the use of COTS components only, a simple ad-hoc custom board is proposed in [21], which can be interfaced with the output of a commercial-grade universal Low-Noise Block (LNB), i.e., the device which down-converts satellite signals from Ku-band (RF) to L-band (IF) for DTH reception. This custom board samples the IF signals at short time intervals (e.g., 1 min) and processes them. The resulting RSL measurements are eventually transmitted to a remote processing server for real-time precipitation monitoring.

In summary, in the case of SMLs, the RSL data can be

obtained from direct measurements and subsequent processing of the microwave satellite signal by either a COTS receiver for DTH services or by an ad-hoc terminal equipped with a custom board.

B. Raw Data Quality Control

Data quality control is fundamental when analyzing measurements collected from OSs. In fact, SML receivers often host commercial-grade equipment, whereas CML hardware can be neither controlled nor accessed by the user of the data. Moreover, in the CML case, even the metadata must be checked and regularly updated as mobile networks are continuously evolving, links undergoing maintenance for a while, being upgraded or sometimes dismissed and replaced by fiber optics.

The Raw Data Quality Control block of Fig. 1 performs a number of basic tests over the time series of RSL and TSL (if available). Standard tests on raw data include:

- a search for missing data, that is, gaps in the time series. Short gaps (with respect to the dynamics of the observed process) can be filled by interpolation;
- the identification of outliers (e.g. glitches or step-like variations in signal power);
- a cross-check of the data collected by different frequency channels of the same link or by nearby links.

A detailed step-by-step data quality control procedure is described in [56].

However, it is recommended to carry out a data quality check also on the outputs of each of the blocks following B in Fig. 1, i.e., on the intermediate outputs as well as on the rainfall products. For instance, the RSL loss due to non-meteorological factors such as temperature effects on the receivers (described later in Section III-B) can be misclassified as light or moderate rain, if samples are processed one-by-one. These patterns can be flagged once the events are identified (i.e. after block E or F), by comparing their features with those of rainfall. A quality control on rainfall products is performed in [19], where outliers are identified cross-checking the rainfall estimates of each OS with those returned by the OSs in the neighborhood. In [57], opportunistic data gathered from CMLs as well as from personal weather stations are considered using a method developed for the latter. An additional quality control can be done on the statistics of the retrieved rainfall events considering monthly, yearly or even longer periods of time as compared with the climatological data of the monitored area [58].

C. Wet/Dry Classification

Labeling the RSL samples as “dry” or “wet” enables the detection of precipitation and the measurement of its duration. Moreover, it helps the subsequent steps of the processing chain in Fig. 1, making it easier to estimate rain intensity. Wet/dry classification algorithms basically exploit the different features of the RSL wet samples w.r.t. the dry ones. For instance, RSL values are rather stable for CMLs in a dry atmosphere, which brings to relatively simple wet/dry classification methods. In

contrast, with SMLs the RSL from GEO satellites, even in the absence of rain, may exhibit 24h fluctuations due to the residual inclination of the satellite orbit w.r.t. the equatorial plane [26]. An operational GEO satellite has an inclination angle (typically lower than 0.1°), which produces SNR fluctuations up to ± 0.5 dB around the nominal level, when an 80-cm receiving parabolic dish is used (see Section III-B for more details). Hence, wet/dry classification methods for SMLs shall take into account this impairment.

1) CMLs

Wet/dry classification can be done on an individual link basis by analyzing the time series of the RSL or of signal attenuation. A simple method consists of calculating the standard deviation of the attenuation level on a sliding window of a suitable duration (e.g. 1 hour). Fluctuations in the signal are detected when the standard deviation exceeds a threshold. The latter is usually defined by training the procedure over dry and wet periods of time previously identified by nearby rainfall sensors [59]. More sophisticated Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods have been used as well. For instance, the authors of [60] apply a technique based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), while [61] adopts a type of recurrent neural network, namely Long Short Term Memory (LSTM). Other methods exploit the spatial correlation of precipitation. In fact, during a rain event, the signals from neighboring CMLs are expected to exhibit similar fluctuations at close temporal intervals [48]. This property becomes more effective where dense CML networks are in place [22]. In [62], the authors propose a one-class classifier based on autoencoders, relying only on dry period data. This method achieves slightly better performance than an approach based on the RSL standard deviation. Wet/dry classification can be done indirectly, as a result of the baseline level calculation [63] (see next subsection). Other approaches make use of independent rainfall sensors, such as weather radars [53] or Earth observation satellites [64], or, again, a combination of the two [65].

2) SMLs

Due to orbit perturbations and drift, GEO satellites, as seen from the Earth, do not appear perfectly still in the sky. As a result, the RSL undergoes slow fluctuations and variations over time scales of hours, which complicate the wet/dry classification task. In this respect, an approach based on two Kalman filters in parallel is effective, as shown in [44], [66]. A Slow Tracker (ST) is configured to track only the slow variations due to orbit perturbations and drift, while a Fast Tracker (FT) detects faster RSL variations, as the ones due to rain. By comparing ST and FT outputs, the start and the end of a rain event can be detected. Kalman filtering can be used as a general method to monitor the RSL and trigger rapid fluctuations due to an external disturbance.

AI methods used for wet/dry classification of SML data include Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Support Vector Machine (SVM) or extremely randomized trees. They are trained using a set of statistical features extracted from the sequence of RSL samples [49], [67], or from a band-pass filtered version of it [68]. AI methods based on observed time

series (that do not require feature extraction) include a deep neural network approach based on a long short-term memory layer [69] or logistic regression based on measurements of the bit error rate. The work in [47] compares four AI algorithms, namely ANN, SVM, decision tree, and random forest. In [70] the same authors propose an online training procedure that includes a forgetting mechanism to increase the efficiency of the wet/dry classification task in embedded systems. In [71] the same authors employ AI to increase the performance of a statistical algorithm over a network of 26 SML links.

D. Baseline Calculation

In principle, signal attenuation along the path can be derived from RSL and TSL measurements and link characteristics through the classical Friis propagation equation [72]. However, not all of the above elements are known. For instance, TSL is not always stored into CML databases and is not available in the case of SMLs. Hence, rain attenuation is usually calculated from the difference (on a dB-scale) between the current RSL value and a RSL “baseline” value calculated in dry conditions (i.e., in the absence of rain).

Baseline estimation methods often rely on the wet/dry classification outcomes working out the baseline value as a statistical index of the RSL distribution over the dry periods before a rain event. For instance, [53] calculates the baseline as the median RSL value over the preceding 24 dry hours. This approach assumes that the baseline is constant during the entire rain event, which may be not the case, especially during long events. In contrast, dynamic techniques update the baseline level at every sample. For instance, [63] takes the minimum RSL over a suitable observation window (31-min with a 1-min raw data sampling), whereas [73] adopts a simple first-order linear low-pass filter. Calibration of the filter coefficient shows that the optimum baseline is the maximum between the previous and the current RSL sample. In principle, dynamic methods can work even without a preliminary wet/dry classification step.

E. Rain Attenuation Calculation

The attenuation produced by rain is eventually evaluated at each sampling instant, based upon the current received RSL sample and the baseline level as follows.

1) CMLs

The RSL is typically the received power (P_R) in dBm. Rain attenuation (in dB) at the generic k th sampling instant is

$$A(k) \text{ [dB]} = P_{BL}(k) - P_R(k) \quad (1)$$

where P_{BL} is the baseline power level in dBm. The above equation assumes that TSL is constant throughout the observation period. However, an Automatic Transmit Power Control (ATPC) loop is usually in place, so that TSL is increased when the RSL falls below a predefined threshold to ensure link availability, for instance, during heavy rain. If ATPC is active, additional information is required to estimate rain attenuation. In principle, the system should collect also the actual TSL time series (P_T), sampled at the same temporal resolution

as the RSL. If TSL is unavailable, data on ATPC magnitude and activation time should be provided, to implement RSL correction strategies [22]. As P_{BL} is usually estimated based on the RSL value in the dry atmosphere, a general expression for rain attenuation in dB with varying TSL is

$$A(k) \text{ [dB]} = P_{BL}(k) - P_R(k) + P_T(k) - P_T^0 \quad (2)$$

where P_T^0 is the nominal TSL, that is, the one in the dry atmosphere (in principle, P_T^0 is the TSL value at the time stamp when $P_{BL}(k)$ was calculated). Rain attenuation calculated through (2) may include, besides the contribution due to falling raindrops, other spurious components, discussed in Sec. III, which should be compensated in advance before converting attenuation into rainfall intensity.

2) SMLs

In the case RSL is a power level, a constant TSL is assumed. Since this value is unknown, the second member of (2) is reduced to the first two terms. If the RSL is instead expressed by the SNR, rain attenuation is given by the following [44]:

$$A(k) = \frac{\bar{\eta}(k)}{\eta(k)} (1 - \xi) + \xi. \quad (3)$$

where $\eta(k)$ is the k th sample of the SNR during a wet interval, $\bar{\eta}(k)$ is the associated baseline level and ξ is a quantity dependent on the components that contribute to the noise level measured at the receiver end. Details of the calculation of total attenuation from the SNR are discussed in Appendix A.

F. Rainfall Intensity Retrieval

Rainfall intensity can be retrieved from rain attenuation taking into account the geometry of the propagation path. The CML and SML scenarios in rain conditions are sketched in Fig. 2 and 3 (as from [74]), respectively. Both figures show a case of stratiform rain, which is characterized by a well defined layered structure. The vertical profile of precipitation is very important in the SML case where the propagation path travels through the whole extent of the troposphere. In this respect, most of SML rainfall retrieval algorithms assume stratiform precipitation, since it is much simpler to model than convective rain. The accuracy of one of these algorithms in the presence of convective rain is assessed in [75] (see their Fig. 8), using RG measurements as ground truth. SMLs tend to underestimate rain intensity when convective precipitation is present. In fact, during the “mature” stage of precipitation, heavy rainfall causes large attenuation values, which may reduce the RSL below the receiver sensitivity. On the other hand, rainfall estimates are rather accurate during the “developing” and the “dissipating” stages of precipitation [76].

Rainfall retrieval algorithms feature the processing steps detailed below yielding an estimate of the rainfall intensity which represents an average value over the wet path, i.e. the rainy portion of length L of the propagation path.

- 1) *Wet link calculation.* Rain intensity may be non uniform neither along the terrestrial path between the transmit and receiving antennas of a CML, nor along a slant SML path between the ground receiver and the top of the clouds.

Fig. 2. CML geometry in the presence of stratiform rain uniformly distributed along the path.

Fig. 3. SML geometry in the presence of stratiform rain uniformly distributed along the path. A two-layer tropospheric model is adopted (as from [74]). The wet fraction of the path goes from ground up to the top of the liquid layer.

In the latter case, precipitation can be also affected by the so-called “virga” phenomenon, i.e., a vertical variation of rainfall intensity with respect to ground level, due to a gradient of atmospheric parameters such as humidity, which can cause evaporation or sublimation of precipitation [77], [20]. As the actual spatial distribution of rain intensity is unknown, the wet path L is usually calculated assuming that the rainfall intensity is constant, both horizontally and vertically, i.e. i) for CML, rain is assumed uniform over the entire path; ii) for SML, rain is uniform over the slant path from the ground station up to the rain height h_R . The latter is defined as the height above mean sea level where solid ice particles start melting into raindrops.

- 2) *Calculation of specific rain attenuation.* The estimated specific (i.e. per unit path length) rain attenuation γ over a wet path of length L at time k is obtained as

$$\gamma(k) \text{ [dB/km]} = A(k) \text{ [dB]} / L \text{ [km]}. \quad (4)$$

- 3) *Rain intensity calculation.* The rain intensity or rain rate $R(k)$ in mm h^{-1} is usually estimated inverting the following γ - R power-law relationship [78]

$$\gamma(k) \text{ [dB/km]} = \alpha R(k)^\kappa \quad (5)$$

yielding

$$R(k) [\text{mm h}^{-1}] = \left(\frac{1}{\alpha L [\text{km}]} A(k) [\text{dB}] \right)^{1/\kappa}. \quad (6)$$

The coefficients α and κ are tabulated by ITU-R [79] as a function of link frequency and polarization. However, even though ITU-R coefficients are largely used in the engineering practice, they represent a coarse average, valid on a statistical basis. In principle, the relationship between R and γ depends also on the microphysics of rain. Therefore, some authors use values of α and κ coefficients calibrated with local disdrometers [80] [81].

The practical implementation of the rain retrieval algorithm has some important differences between CMLs and SMLs, detailed in the following.

1) CMLs

The radio link of length L between two antennas of a mobile network is shown schematically in Fig. 2. The link path is often nearly horizontal, i.e., the path inclination angle θ is close to 0° . Especially for links longer than a few kilometers, and depending on local climate, it is possible, up to very likely, that the rainfall is not homogeneous along the path. However, since no information on the spatial distribution of precipitation along the link can be obtained from rain attenuation measurements, rainfall estimates from CMLs always represent average rain rate values along the entire link, rather than just along the wet path.

2) SMLs

The radio downlink between a satellite and a ground station for uniform stratiform precipitation and a simple two-layer tropospheric model is schematically shown in Fig. 3. We assume a clear separation, at the rain height h_R , between two layers: i) the upper layer, named the Ice Particle Layer (IPL), mostly made of ice in the form of frozen dry particles, and ii) the lower layer, named Liquid Layer (LL), which extends down to ground and it is characterized by the presence of liquid precipitation. The ground station is located at an altitude h_S above mean sea level and sees the satellite at an elevation angle θ above the horizon. The evaluation of the length of the wet path requires the knowledge of h_R , which is dependent on the zero-degree isotherm height h_0 . Accurate estimates of h_R can be derived from real-time data, such as temperature at ground, observations from zenith-pointing WRs or radiosonde measurements. However, this approach can be employed for few measuring sites, usually for calibration and validation purposes, while it is not practical if a widespread network of sensors is in place, due to complexity and cost. A valid alternative for obtaining near real-time estimates of h_R is to build from statistical data, mainly modeled on past observations. For instance, worldwide yearly average values for h_R can be derived from the corresponding h_0 values by the simple scaling law $h_R = h_0 + 0.36 \text{ km}$ [82]. A more accurate estimate of h_R can be gathered from short-term forecasts of h_0 produced by a mesoscale numerical

weather prediction model, such as the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model [83] or the High Resolution (HRES) model of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) [84]. This approach is a good compromise between accuracy and computational effort. Furthermore, the complexity of tropospheric phenomena leads to the adoption of more sophisticated propagation models. The rain height rarely coincides with the zero degree isotherm due to the presence of the Melting Layer (ML), i.e. the intermediate layer between the IPL and the LL, where the ice particles falling from the clouds gradually melt into raindrops [44]. In this case, the three steps outlined above are incorporated into an analytical formula that accounts for the geometry of the multiple tropospheric layers with the associated propagation features, taking the k th sample of total attenuation $A(k)$ as the input parameter, and the associated rain rate $R(k)$ as the unknown [44].

III. A BROAD CLASSIFICATION OF DISTURBANCES AFFECTING OS SIGNALS

OS raw data are affected by several disturbances, which must be identified and, when possible, compensated for by the Raw Data Quality Control block of the processing chain in Fig. 1, or at a later stage. Some of these effects have been investigated by using radar data to simulate CML path attenuation [85] or by elaborating from analytical models [86]. It is convenient to classify disturbances into three broad classes:

- effects due to electromagnetic wave propagation from the transmitter to the receiver (Section III-A);
- effects due to the interaction between link components (e.g., antennas, receiver, etc.) and the environment as well as to non-ideal functioning, or malfunctioning of the hardware itself (Section III-B);
- effects due to technical limitations of CMLs and SMLs when used as rainfall sensors. (Section III-C).

A. Propagation effects

They can be further divided into those due to the interaction with atmospheric constituents (i.e., gases) or with the atmospheric particles sometimes present in the air, and those with objects interfering with the propagation path. The impact of these interactions on the received signal depends on many factors:

- Characteristics of the signal, that is, frequency, polarization, and size of the electromagnetic beam in the plane transverse to the propagation direction.
- Path length and path elevation angle.
- Characteristics of atmospheric particles (chemical composition, phase, shape, size, and number concentration).
- Climatology of the site where the link is installed including microclimatic effects.
- Height of the transmitting and receiving antennas above ground.
- Type of the surrounding environment (i.e., rural, suburban, urban, etc).

Fig. 4. Gas attenuation as a function of frequency over terrestrial (0°) and slant paths with two different atmospheric conditions.

Fig. 5. Fog/cloud attenuation per 1 km path length as a function of the LWC at five different frequencies.

The effects on the received signal are attenuation, i.e., loss of signal power measured at the receiver end with respect to propagation in free space, signal fluctuations around its mean value, and cross-polarization, i.e., partial transfer of signal power from the transmitted polarization to the orthogonal one. These impairments have been extensively studied and many empirical and theoretical models are available [72], [87]–[90].

Propagation effects are usually modeled as additive random processes. In this respect, signal attenuation in (2) and (3) should be intended as an average over a time window short enough to track variations in rainfall intensity but long enough to average out signal fluctuations due to effects such as the continuous reshuffling of raindrops within the electromagnetic beam and the additive noise introduced by the receiver.

1) Interaction with atmospheric components

In the frequency bands listed in Table I, raindrops generally have the highest impact on the RSL. However, significant or, at least, non-negligible effects can be produced by a plethora of other atmospheric components:

- gas absorption, in particular due to water vapor and oxygen (O_2) [91];
- clouds (for SMLs and for CMLs in mountainous environments), fog and mist [92];
- other types of hydrometeors, e.g., snow, hail, sleet, etc. [93];
- dust and sand storms [94];
- ash and dust from volcanic emissions [95];
- tropospheric scintillation (SMLs only) [96], [97].

Gasses are ever-present components, although the water vapor contribution is time-variant even during rainfall due to humidity variations. Beyond 10 GHz, atmospheric gases may significantly contribute to path attenuation due to the presence of two major absorption peaks produced by water vapor and oxygen at 23 and 60 GHz, respectively. Fig. 4 shows the frequency dependence of gas attenuation for three different path elevation angles and two different atmospheric conditions corresponding to summer and winter at mid-latitude, according to ITU-R definitions [91] [98]. The curves at 40° and 90° (i.e., zenith) elevation are calculated across a path from sea level

to 10 km height, while the curves for horizontal terrestrial paths are derived assuming, for convenience, a path length of 1 km. The average value of gas attenuation over a 40° satellite link at 20 GHz is around 0.6 dB, i.e., the same as a 3 km terrestrial link. With CML path lengths of 5 km, which are not uncommon in mobile networks, especially outside city areas, the average gas attenuation is about 1 dB in summer (at 20 GHz), which corresponds to a rainfall intensity of 2 mm h^{-1} at the same frequency.

Fog and clouds are made by micrometric water droplets suspended in the air. The corresponding attenuation turns out to be proportional to the Liquid Water Content (LWC) in the air, i.e., the mass of water particles in a unit volume of air. The attenuation across a 1 km path through fog/clouds is shown in Fig. 5 at five different frequencies. The LWC of fog and clouds can range over orders of magnitude. As for fog, a LWC value of 0.1 g m^{-3} corresponds to dense radiation fog (visibility in the order of 100 m), while the LWC of heavy advection fog can be as high as 0.2 g m^{-3} . The LWC of clouds depends on the environment (i.e., maritime or continental) and on the type of cloud. Moreover, it is a function of the height above cloud base. The climatologic Complementary Cumulative Distribution Function (CCDF) of cloud attenuation (dB), derived through the ITU-R model [92], is shown in Fig. 6 for satellite links at three different elevation angles in the Ku- and Ka-bands, respectively. The curves are terminated at 1% of time, as it is assumed that rain attenuation dominates at lower percentages of time. Although gas and clouds produce maximum attenuation levels comparable to light rain, they may end in large overestimates of the accumulated rain, during long low-intensity events, if these components are not compensated for.

Melting ice particles and wet snow are able to produce large attenuation values over Earth-space links and even over terrestrial links, depending on the height of the link with respect to the rain height, which, in turn, depends on the geographic location and is time-variant. [99] proposes a method to discriminate between rain and sleet (i.e., a mixture of rain and snow), from CML data only. ITU-R [93] provides a correction

Fig. 6. CCDF of cloud attenuation for SMLs in the Ku- and Ka-band at three different locations.

factor for specific attenuation as a function of the difference between the height of the propagation path and the rain height. The contribution of melting ice particles is significant from the rain height down to 1200 meters below it, whereas attenuation due to ice particles above the rain height is negligible. Specific attenuation in the ML can be up to 3.5 times the one of rain at an equivalent liquid precipitation rate [100].

Wireless links operating in the microwave and millimeter wave range of frequencies are severely affected by sand storms and dust storms. These events are frequent in the dry regions of the world (e.g. Central Asia, Middle East, southwestern United States, etc.). A comprehensive review of attenuation measurements and propagation models through sand storms and dust storms is in [94]. Attenuation increases as frequency increases and visibility decreases. Moreover, humidity has a huge impact on attenuation as it changes the dielectric constant of dust particles. Specific attenuation values in excess of 10 dB km^{-1} were measured at 21.3 GHz during severe dust storms in Khartoum (Sudan) [101].

Volcanic eruptions are rare and sudden events that can have a significant impact on satellite communications, especially when large amounts of volcanic particles and gases are expelled in the atmosphere. An example is the eruption of the Eyjafjallajökull volcano in April 2010. The event triggered an ash cloud up to 9 km in height, causing significant attenuation at frequencies above 10 GHz [102].

Tropospheric scintillations are rapid amplitude fluctuations caused by small-scale irregularities in the refractive index of the air. They are not negligible for SMLs at frequencies above 10 GHz and increase with frequency. In the Ku-band, fluctuations are within $\pm 0.5 \text{ dB}$ and the period of scintillation fades varies from 1 to 10 s [96]. Therefore, these fluctuations are faster than signal variations during rain events.

2) Interference effects

CMLs are usually mounted on tall masts and they are carefully designed to prevent the electromagnetic wave from interacting with neighboring objects before reaching the receiver. It is usually considered that such interference is negligible if a region of space around the transmitter-receiver line-of-sight axis, known as the first Fresnel ellipsoid, is mostly free from

obstacles. For instance, a 5 km link at 20 GHz has a loss within 0.5 dB due to partial clearance of the first Fresnel ellipsoid, if an area of a 7 m radius around the line-of-sight axis is free from obstacles at the midway point of the link. Possible sources of interference are:

- Foliage: it may induce only a partial clearance of the Fresnel ellipsoid, especially during spring and summer.
- Multipath propagation: indirect signals may reach the receiver, for instance after ground reflection.

B. Environment effects on the sensor

Inspection of CML and SML signals sometimes highlights peculiar patterns that are not related to propagation effects but rather to the interaction of the sensor with the environment.

1) CMLs and SMLs common disturbances

Reported sources of environmental disturbances that affect both types of sensors are:

- *Rain, snow, and dew over the antenna:* The thin layer of water deposited by rainfall on the antenna (or on the antenna radome) can produce a significant extra attenuation. Wet Antenna Attenuation (WAA) adds-up to rainfall attenuation while it is raining and it is present even after the rain event, depending on the duration of the antenna drying process. If WAA is not accounted, rainfall intensity may be heavily overestimated. Direct measurements of WAA require ad-doc set-ups, for instance, elevated sprinklers directing sprays of water to the antenna, which can simulate rain of different intensity [103]. Indirect measurements have been made by taking the difference between total link attenuation during rain and rainfall attenuation. The latter was calculated, for example, by electromagnetic theory from the Drop Size Distribution (DSD) data collected by an array of disdrometers deployed along the path [104]. As measurements are expensive and, in principle, they should be carried out on each link in the network, WAA is usually estimated through empirical models. These models predict WAA from total attenuation (i.e., the difference between TSL and RSL), from rain attenuation, measured by the CML [103] [105] or from rainfall intensity, measured by either RGs [106] or by WRs [24], through simple analytical functions. The model parameters are calibrated using nearby RGs, or the parameters values derived in the original papers are assumed. The majority of models available for CML data predict an increase of WAA with rainfall intensity. For instance, the expressions proposed by [103] and [106], and derived from data at similar frequencies (27 and 32 GHz, respectively), predict WAA values slightly above 2.5 dB at 50 mm/h. These values are not negligible at all when compared with rain attenuation, that is, about 9 dB/km at 32 GHz [79]. Due to the several factors that affect WAA, including frequency, antenna set-up and elevation angle and weather conditions, it is recommended to calibrate CMLs by independent rainfall measurements.

On the other hand, there is no evidence of any appreciable WAA effect in SML setups for DTH satellite

TV reception featuring offset parabolic reflectors. This type of reflectors exhibits a more vertical surface, when compared to center-fed designs, which are rarely used for DTH reception. As a result, offset reflectors are less exposed to direct rain impact, thus reducing the effectivity of WAA.

Concerning snow and ice effects, a significant overestimation of the precipitation has been found in a CML-based countrywide study in Germany during the cold season, arguably due to the combined effect of melting snow along the path and ice and snow accumulation on the reflector surfaces [24]. Similarly, snow accumulation on the user terminal antennas at high-latitude has been found to cause severe attenuation on Ka-band satellite links for a significant fraction of time [107].

- *Thermal effects:* They have an impact on RF circuits and antenna components such as reflectors, as well as on mountings and masts. In the case of CMLs, this results in slow and regular oscillations of the RSL with a clear daily pattern during warm sunny days. The magnitude of temperature often triggers this effect. Thermal effects may lead to label dry slots as wet or to errors in the estimate of the baseline level, which, in turn, is used to derive rainfall intensity. An example is shown in Fig. 7. SML systems relying on commercial grade components for satellite TV reception are also prone to thermal effects. In particular, the LNB, which is mounted in the focus of the parabolic reflector, is exposed to sun rays and turns out the most vulnerable component to external temperatures. In this respect, the manufacturing quality, hence the cost of the device can make a significant difference in the sensitivity to thermal effects [108], as shown in Fig. 8. The upper chart presents the recorded RSL over a 24-h interval on a sunny and warm day (max. temperature 28°C) for both a conventional low-cost LNB (approximate cost 10 €), and a SmartLNB device (approximate cost a few hundreds of €), plotted as green and red lines, respectively. The bottom chart compares the fast-varying additive noise component affecting the two RSL records. As apparent, the cheaper LNB reveals a remarkable noise increase, strongly correlated with the external temperature (in blue), while the high performance SmartLNB is almost insensitive to temperature variations.
- *Wind loading:* it may lead to misalignment, which, in turn, may cause an extra attenuation dependent on the inclination angle of the antenna pole with respect to the line-of-sight propagation direction. The inclination angle has a static and a dynamic component, the latter being due to the vibration frequency of the pole [109]. Both components are proportional to the square of wind velocity through a coefficient dependent on the type and length of the pole. Wind gusts can be responsible of misalignment and realignment events, that is, a sharp decrease or increase of the RSL.
- *Link malfunctioning:* it produces several unwanted effects on the RSL, which can be usually detected by visual inspection. In case of CMLs, the most common anomalies

Fig. 7. Top: four-day record of RSL from a CML (41.082 GHz, 1.332 m), showing a rain event and thermal effects, bottom: corresponding temperature record highlighting the daily cycle. The RSL signal format is 15-min MIN-MAX.

Fig. 8. Top: 24-h RSL record collected by an SML equipped with a SmartLNB (red) and by one with a conventional LNB (green). Bottom: corresponding fast noise component affecting the SmartLNB (red) and the conventional LNB (green) and daily temperature cycle (blue). The RSL signal is the instantaneous SNR sampled every 30 s.

are glitches, that is, sudden and short discontinuities in the signal (usually dips). An abnormal decrease of the RSL is sometimes observed, for instance, during heavy rain events due to water dropping into the antenna feed. Finally, the no signal status is observed for long periods during maintenance, for lack of power or link dismissal. Link failures may be seldom experienced by

Fig. 9. Cumulative sum of the percentage of missing data for two different CML datasets in Italy. The Valmalenco dataset includes 17 CMLs, whereas the Emilia-Romagna dataset has 149.

SMLs, due to operator’s house-keeping maneuvers, power adjustment, TV channel re-configuration, etc.

It is interesting to assess the percentage of OS raw data that are either missing or invalid. For the sake of brevity, we indicate such a case as NaN (Not a Number). A NaN occurs at discrete time k if $RSL(k, i, n) = \text{NaN}$ or $TSL(k, i, n) = \text{NaN}$, where i and n denote link and channel indices, respectively (channel perspective). Alternatively, from a link perspective, a NaN is when $RSL(k, i, n) = \text{NaN}$ or $TSL(k, i, n) = \text{NaN}$ for every n , that is, if every link channel is NaN. Fig. 9 shows the cumulative sum of the percentage of NaNs for two different CML datasets. The top panel shows the results for a set of 17 links in the area of Valmalenco (Lombardy), during a non-continuous observation period of 1056 hours in 2019. The bottom panel shows NaNs on the raw data collected from a network of 151 CMLs in Emilia-Romagna (owned by a different MNO), during a continuous observation window of 4344 hours. Data are sampled every 1 min. In the Valmalenco dataset, the percentage of NaNs (raw data) is less than 4% for all links and is within 2% for 15 out of 17 links. In the Emilia-Romagna dataset, 142 out of 149 links (95% of the network) have less than 2% of NaNs. An analysis of data availability for the OpenMRG CML dataset [110], which includes 364 two-way links, that is, 728 channels or sublinks according to the authors nomenclature, shows that 93% of the sublinks successfully collected more than 99% of data.

2) SMLs peculiar disturbances

Due to the different link geometry, the following disturbances are peculiar to SMLs.

- *Orbit Perturbations*: The orbit of any GEO satellite is slightly inclined w.r.t. the equatorial plane, as a result of the gravitational effect induced by the Moon and the Sun. This implies that the satellite does not appear still in the sky when observed by a ground terminal. Instead it moves around its nominal position along an eight-shaped path with a 24-h period [111] [112]. The corresponding angular variations, though small, are not negligible due

Fig. 10. Record of downlink RSL from a GEO satellite, showing several different impairments. The RSL signal format is the instantaneous E_s/N_0 at 1-min sampling interval.

to the narrow beam of the parabolic dish (Fig. 10). By consequence, the RSL exhibits a 24-h periodic fluctuation. Further variations of the RSL are caused by the slow longitudinal drift of the satellite under the action of the gravitational forces caused by the longitudinal mass variations of the Earth. To counteract these perturbations, the satellite position is periodically corrected by the satellite operator with “East-West” and “North-South” station-keeping maneuvers [113]. The combination of longitudinal drift and maneuvers renders the deterministic compensation of RSL fluctuations impractical.

- *Sun transit*: Twice a year, around equinoxes, a GEO satellite is “blinded” by the apparent transit of the Sun behind the satellite. This phenomenon lasts about 20 minutes every day at the same time for a dozen of days (Fig. 10). During the sun transit, the Sun causes an increase of the noise temperature of the ground receiver [114], which may result in a degradation or in the complete loss of the signal.
- *Adjustments of transponder transmit power*: Occasionally, the satellite operator changes the transponder gain settings due to customer requests or other operational needs. This adjustment is normally carried out in a very short time and sometimes it may result in a reduction of the RSL (Fig. 10).

C. Technical limitations

When CMLs or SMLs are used as rainfall sensors, they have technical limitations, which bound their accuracy and reliability, even in the ideal case the disturbances described in Sections III-A and III-B are fully compensated. Some major limitations are listed below.

- *Temporal sampling:* CML raw data are often decimated before being stored and transmitted through the network to minimize bandwidth occupation, as data are collected from thousands of devices. As a result, the temporal sampling of the available data ranges from less than 1-min, which is finer than the one of CSs (see Table I), to 15-min, which may be too coarse to track the dynamics of rapidly changing convective cells. On the other hand, SML data sampling depends on the technical characteristics of the receiving devices. For instance, SmartLNBS sample the RSL at a fixed rate of one sample per second and return one averaged RSL value every 30 or 60 seconds (selectable by the user) [44]. Systems featuring ad-hoc custom boards interfaced with conventional LNBS as the one described in [43], provide raw data averaged over similar time scales as SmartLNBS. Other satellite receivers may have different (typically coarser) time resolutions. For instance, data from ViaSat’s SurfBeam® 2 terminals [115] that are used in the Konnect™ satellite platform for two-way broadband access in Ka-band [116], are collected and processed by the MNO service center every 15 minutes [117].
- *Spatial sampling:* Individual CMLs and SMLs produce path-integrated rainfall intensity estimates across horizontal and slant paths, respectively. In addition, the quantity actually measured by a link is the average rain attenuation across the path, rather than the rainfall intensity. These facts have two important consequences. First, as (6) is not linear, the retrieved rainfall intensity is not the arithmetic average across the path but instead an equivalent rainfall intensity. Please note that, substituting ITU-R coefficient values [79] into (5), then (6) turns out to be almost linear between 18.3 GHz and 24.9 GHz, depending on polarization and path elevation. Second, CMLs and SMLs are often modeled as point sensors located midway through the path. Some authors suggest to approximate the spatial distribution of rainfall across the path by two or more virtual RGs, deriving the rainfall intensity in each of the above points by an iterative method relying on nearby links [118].
The non-uniformity of the rain field along the wet segment is tackled by several works, usually on a statistical basis, i.e. applying a path-reduction factor to the rain attenuation value corresponding to a given probability level of the CCDF curve [93], [119]–[121]. For instance, [121] adopts a physical approach, modeling the spatial structure of the precipitation field by simple cylindrically-shaped rain cell(s) filled with uniform rain, as shown in Fig. 11. The path-reduction factor depends on link parameters (i.e., length of the wet segment and elevation angle), as well as on the features of the rain cells, in particular: *i)* the diameter of a single rain cell; *ii)* the average length of the intersection between the ground projections of the slant path and of the individual rain cells; *iii)* a calibration coefficient that considers the non-uniform distribution of rain inside a cell. The characteristic of the cells can be obtained, for instance by a dataset of WR observations.
- *Rainfall field reconstruction:* Retrieving 2D rainfall maps

Fig. 11. Precipitation along a CML path (top) and an SML path (bottom), modeled by several cylindrically-shaped rainfall cells with uniform rain intensity inside.

from 1D measurements has obvious limitations. The spatial reconstruction of the rainfall field from CML data is bounded by the density and the topology of the mesh of available links. It is usually done by interpolation techniques such as inverse distance weighting or ordinary kriging [24], [122]–[124]. More sophisticated approaches include the adoption of rainfall advection models [125] or tomographic methods [126], [127]. To date, there are very few studies based on SML data. Some examples with synthetic rain are illustrated in [128], [129]. The availability of many terminals of the EUROBUS satellite network [45], currently operated by MBI Srl (Pisa, Italy) allowed the spatial reconstruction of the catastrophic flood event that devastated Germany, in 2021, using both interpolation [130], [131], and an innovative Ensemble-Kalman Filter algorithm [132].

- *Link characteristics:* The different combinations of path length and operation frequency among the CMLs of a mobile network and between CMLs and SMLs lead to different performance when they are used as rain intensity sensors, in terms of sensitivity, defined as the minimum detectable rainfall intensity and range of measurable rainfall intensities. Moreover, in the CML case, the usage of different antenna set-ups may lead to a different impact of WAA on different links, hence, in principle, prompting for link calibration on an individual basis.
- *Signal format:* in the case of CML data, TSL and RSL are stored for purposes of link quality control. Hence, the data format is often not optimized for obtaining quantitative precipitation estimates, which results in
 - sub-optimal sampling strategy;
 - inaccuracy due to signal quantization.

Fig. 12. Effect of RSL quantization for two values of the quantization error: 1 dB (solid) and 0.1 dB (dashed). Left: minimum detectable rainfall intensity against path length at four different frequencies. Right: accuracy of rainfall intensity estimate against true rainfall intensity for different combinations of path length and frequency.

A MINMAX sampling strategy is sometimes implemented, that is, minimum and maximum RSL are measured within a given time window instead of the average RSL value. Algorithms for estimating the average rainfall intensity from RSL extremes have been developed by [53] and [133]. Fig. 12 shows the impact of RSL quantization error on the sensitivity of CMLs and on their accuracy in estimating rainfall intensity. Four frequencies and two values of the quantization error are considered (0.1 and 1 dB), corresponding to lower and upper bounds for the datasets available in the open literature. Path length values are bounded to detect maximum rainfall intensity values corresponding to a maximum allowable rain attenuation of 50 dB. A 1 dB quantization error produces a substantial decrease of the minimum detectable rainfall intensity (left panel of Fig. 12) as links at frequency below about 20 GHz are not sensitive to light rain (1 mm h^{-1}). Moreover, the accuracy is within 20% only if rainfall intensity is above 10 mm h^{-1} and frequency is in the Ku-band or above (right panel). Hence, if CMLs will be used in the future for operational purposes, the raw data should have a quantization error in the order of 0.1 dB.

- *RSL-to-rainfall intensity conversion*: the conversion formula (5) with ITU-R coefficients is used in many studies based on OSs. However, it does not account for the microphysics of rain. The usage of $\gamma - R$ relationships obtained from local data is more representative of the climatology of the area of interest. As an example, Fig. 13 shows (5) at Ku- and Ka-band (solid black lines) and the relationships obtained from data collected in Rome (Italy) by two different types of disdrometers, i.e., an OTT Parsivel sensor and a 2D Video Disdrometer (2DVD), the latter being considered the benchmark for DSD measurements. While OTT Parsivel and 2DVD are in good agreement, there are differences with the ITU-R relationship in particular at Ka-band and at high rainfall intensities. Furthermore, using disdrometer and WR data,

the authors of [75] quantified errors in rainfall rate retrievals from SMLs produced by the ML geometry (height and thickness) and by the propagation models that derive attenuation from the precipitation rate in the LL and in the ML, i.e., the power-law model (with the coefficients derived from disdrometer data) and Dissanayake model [134], respectively. The results highlight a limited impact of the above factors (Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) $< 1 \text{ mm h}^{-1}$ and Normalized Mean Absolute Error (NMAE) $< 20\%$). These results need to be confirmed by data from other climatic locations and checked over a wider range of rainfall regimes.

- *Dynamic range*: Any SML receiver is characterized by a threshold RSL_{\min} , which represents the lowest usable value of RSL. Therefore, when RSL falls below RSL_{\min} , the device is no longer capable of measuring its actual value. This is called an outage and it may occur during heavy precipitation. Hence, the rain rate corresponding to RSL_{\min} represents the saturation value of the rain estimator, i.e., the maximum value that can be measured before the outage occurs. An as example, Fig. 14 shows the performance of the SmartLNB system described in [44], wherein data processed are transmitted by the satellite Eutelsat 10 A in Ku-band (11.345 GHz), and collected by an 80 cm dish located in Pisa, Italy. The nominal SNR value in clear sky conditions is 11 dB, whereas the minimum SNR before outage is equal to -2 dB . The three curves convert the above 13 dB dynamic range into an interval of observable rain intensities, for three different values of the zero-degree isotherm height, which represent a lower bound, an upper bound and the yearly average in the measurement area, respectively. The dynamic range of CMLs is generally much higher than the one of SMLs as CMLs are part of back-hauling networks, which have very high availability requirements (typically 99.99% or even higher). In many cases, fade mitigation techniques such as ATPC are used to increase

Fig. 13. $\gamma - R$ scatterplots obtained from DSD data measured with two different disdrometers (OTT Parsivel and 2DVD HyMeX), in Rome (Italy). The specific attenuation γ is calculated at Ka-band (top) and at Ku-band (bottom). The dashed and dash-dotted black lines in each graph are power-law best fits to the measured data, while the solid black line is the relationship provided by the ITU-R model [79].

the dynamic range if heavy rain is present across the path. An analysis of gaps in CML data due to heavy rain is carried out in [58].

- **Data transfer:** RSL data and other link quality indicators are usually logged by the network management systems provided by CML vendors. However, the format of these data is not optimized for weather monitoring. Alternatively, data can be polled through custom software based on protocols such as SNMP (Simple Network Management Protocol) [135]. Transferring data from thousands of CMLs in a countrywide network to a cloud server for processing may be an issue, especially if real-time applications are targeted. Future systems may leverage edge computing for local processing of RSL data, reducing data transmission bottlenecks in large-scale OS networks.

D. Mitigation of disturbances

Assessing unwanted effects by automatic tests is not straightforward and sometimes the task is done by visual

Fig. 14. Dynamic range of an SML receiver expressed as estimated rain rate as a function of the measured SNR, i.e. E_s/N_0 . If the SNR falls below -2 dB, the system is in outage. The three curves represent three different wet path lengths, corresponding to as many values of the 0°C isotherm height.

inspection of signal patterns. In general, two classes of tests should be run:

- 1) check the pattern of all events to avoid misclassifying unwanted effects as rain events;
- 2) when it is raining, quantify and separate unwanted effects from rainfall attenuation.

Please note that, if dry/wet classification is done based on CML or SML data only, it may result in flagging dry periods as wet, for instance during thermal events.

Using concurrent weather data is recommended to help identifying disturbances related to atmospheric and environmental conditions. Gas attenuation can be accurately predicted by the ITU-R model [91] from standard meteorological data (pressure, temperature and relative humidity) that are collected from local weather stations. A procedure for correcting the baseline value according to predicted gas attenuation is described in [136]. Cloud attenuation detected by CMLs or by SML terminals at Ku-band is within 0.5 dB, while it is up to about 1 dB at Ka-band. As cloud events are not easily predictable from meteorological data, values of attenuation produced by clouds should be classified in advance as non-precipitation events and discarded. Identifying events due to other factors than rain is basically a pattern recognition problem and it is obviously more challenging for real-time applications than in the case of analysis over historical data. Thermal effects are usually produced by temperature-induced variations in the amplifier gain at the received end. Sometimes, on-device compensation is carried out. As temperature triggers the process, data from weather stations may help in elaborating algorithms to correct or to identify thermal events. However, RSL dips due to thermal effects such as the ones in Fig. 7 are rather easy to distinguish from rain as they exhibit a mild pattern correlated with the daily temperature cycle. A mere machine-learning approach based on features such as the derivative of RSL and the difference between minimum and maximum RSL (in the case of MINMAX data) could be effective.

SML peculiar disturbances produced by GEO satellite orbit perturbations can be mitigated by averaging the baseline level over suitable time-windows. Satellite diversity reception using a multi-LNB receiver setup is a possible strategy to counteract

signal loss due to sun transit effects [137].

IV. KPIS OF OS RAINFALL ESTIMATION ACCURACY

Data gathered from CMLs and SMLs, as well as other opportunistic or non professional sensors, bring added value if they are validated against CSs, through rigorous procedures. In this process, RG and WR data are usually taken as the ground truth. The quantities that are usually compared with the ground truth are rainfall occurrence (i.e., the output of wet/dry classification) and rainfall intensity averaged over a suitable observation period. Various metrics, often referred to as KPIS, are considered to compare the performance of OSs and CSs in detecting and quantifying rainfall. In the following, we first investigate few important aspects that affect the calculation of KPIS, namely, the different spatial and temporal sampling of different rainfall sensors and the uneven characteristics of rainfall itself. Then, in Section IV-A and IV-B, we discuss the KPIS used for rainfall occurrence and rainfall intensity estimates, respectively, surveying the works on this topic.

The calculation of the KPIS requires to associate each OS with one or several CSs. The different spatial sampling of the sensors prompts different association strategies. CMLs and SMLs provide path-averaged rainfall estimates over horizontal or slanted paths, whereas RGs collect data at a single point. Finally, WRs carry out volume scans at different elevation angles, which are subsequently combined and projected on the ground, resulting in rainfall products available over 2D spatial grids. CML and SML data can be compared with WRs products by selecting the pixels of the radar grid that overlap the projected link path on the ground. The radar pixels are typically weighted by the fraction of the path that lies within each of them [24]. Please note that the value of each (cartesian) radar pixel (a dry/wet flag or a rainfall intensity value) is a spatial average of measurements collected aloft by scanning volumes of space in spherical coordinates. Instead, RGs are usually associated with CMLs or SMLs by calculating the geometric distance between each RG and the nearest point, or the midpoint of the link path [123], [138]. An effective distance, which accounts for the path length and its relative position w.r.t. the RG can be obtained by breaking the path into shorter segments and averaging the distances from the RG to the midpoint of each segment [81]. The minimum distance rule is the most obvious rationale used for the association. Alternatively, all the RGs within a maximum distance D_{max} from the link are selected and the ground truth is a linear combination of the RG measurements within D_{max} [139]. As a general rule, D_{max} should be lower than the spatial decorrelation distance of precipitation. For example, a study in Emilia-Romagna region (Italy) shows that KPIS are insensitive to the distance between CMLs and RGs, as long as $D_{max} < 3$ km [22]. This value is significantly shorter than the average decorrelation distance of precipitation in Italy [140] and, in addition, it is shorter than the length of the CMLs used in [22]. To conclude, associating CML or SML data to WR data is straightforward as the radar grid covers the entire link path. On the other hand, RG point measurements are representative of only a part of the path, depending on the

relative position of the RG w.r.t. the link, and on the length of the path.

OS and CS data may have rather different temporal sampling, ranging from a few seconds to hourly or daily in the case of RG data. In general, it is observed that the agreement between OS data and ground truth improves as the integration time increases (see Table V). In fact, in the case of comparison between CMLs or SMLs and RGs (i.e., point sensors), increasing the integration time mitigates the effect of the spatial distribution of rain, even though it reduces the number of data points available to perform a solid statistical analysis. As a practical guideline, the use of a sub-daily integration time scale, such as hourly intervals, can serve as an effective starting point. This approach can balance the need to capture detailed temporal variations with the requirement of maintaining a sufficiently large sample size for meaningful comparisons.

Rainfall is observed in a small fraction of time, usually lower than 10% in continental areas at mid-latitude. In addition, the statistical distribution of rainfall intensity is skewed toward small values. Hence, it is important to rely on KPIS of wet/dry classification that accounts for data imbalance. Moreover, the calculation of KPIS of rain intensity estimates should be restricted to OS-CS pairs of samples with rain intensity values that exceed a minimum intensity threshold for both the OS estimate and the ground truth measurement. Otherwise, the calculation can be done in the cases where only the ground truth sample is above the threshold. Finally, when calculating rainfall intensity KPIS based on relative errors, small deviations from very low “true” values can lead to disproportionately high relative errors due to division by near-zero reference amounts.

A. KPIS for wet/dry classification

Wet/dry classification is a binary problem, where rainy (i.e., wet) observations are labeled as positive samples, while non-rainy (i.e., dry) observations are labeled as negative. The labels are assigned by thresholding the rainfall intensity measured by CSs, taken as ground truth. In the case of RGs, the threshold is usually set based on the number of tips per unit time. Similarly, in the case of WRs, a pixel is declared wet when the rainfall intensity (averaged over the pixel area) exceeds a certain threshold.

When comparing CMLs or SMLs with WRs, a link is flagged wet or dry if the rainfall intensity value calculated from the weighted average of the overlapping radar pixels exceeds a threshold. As for comparison with RGs, the link is given the same wet/dry label as the nearest RG, or according to the most probable wet/dry outcome obtained combining nearby RGs. The above tags are the true wet/dry assignments as they are based on ground truth data, which must be compared with the wet/dry tags estimated from CML or SML data. The latter are not determined by thresholding the rainfall intensity as wet/dry classification is a specific task that comes before rainfall intensity estimate in the processing chain of OS data (see Fig. 1). Instead, statistical or AI algorithms are used to label wet/dry time intervals.

TABLE II
MOST SIGNIFICANT KPIS FOR THE WET/DRY CLASSIFICATION PROBLEM.

Metric	Formula	Description
Specificity (Spe)	$\frac{TN}{n_{dry}}$	Indicates the classifier ability to predict dry observations. It ranges between 0 (worst score) and 1 (best score).
False Positive Ratio (FPR)	$\frac{FP}{n_{dry}}$	The complementary of Specificity, indicating the classifier inability to predict dry observations. It ranges between 0 (best score) and 1 (worst score).
False Alarm Ratio (FAR)	$\frac{FP}{n_{c,wet}}$	It is the ratio of false alarms to predicted true samples. It ranges between 0 (best score) and 1 (worst score).
Recall (Rec)	$\frac{TP}{n_{wet}}$	Indicates the classifier ability to predict wet observations. It is also referred to as Sensitivity or Probability of Detection. It ranges between 0 (worst score) and 1 (best score).
False Negative Ratio (FNR)	$\frac{FN}{n_{wet}}$	The complementary of the Rec metric, indicating the classifier inability to predict wet observations. It ranges between 0 (best score) and 1 (worst score).
Equitable Threat Score (ETS)	$\frac{TP - \frac{n_{wet} \cdot n_{c,wet}}{n_{dry} + n_{wet}}}{n_{wet} + FP - \frac{n_{wet} \cdot n_{c,wet}}{n_{dry} + n_{wet}}}$	Provides a better measure of a classifier's true skill to predict wet observations. It ranges from -1/3 to 1, where -1/3 is the worst score, 0 means no skill, and 1 is the best score.
Harmonic Mean (HM)	$\frac{2 \cdot \text{Spe} \cdot \text{Rec}}{\text{Spe} + \text{Rec}}$	It is the harmonic mean between Spe and Rec metrics. It ranges between 0 (worst score) and 1 (best score).
Mean Detection Error (MDE)	$0.5 \cdot \left(\frac{FN}{n_{wet}} + \frac{FP}{n_{dry}} \right)$	It is the average of the missed wet and false wet rates. It ranges between 0 (best score) and 1 (worst score).
Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC)	$\frac{TP \cdot TN - FP \cdot FN}{\sqrt{n_{wet} \cdot n_{dry} \cdot n_{c,dry} \cdot n_{c,wet}}}$	It summarizes the four values of the confusion matrix in a single measure. It ranges from -1 to +1, where -1 indicates perfect misclassification, +1 indicates perfect classification, and 0 indicates a performance not better than random guessing.

The KPIS used to assess wet/dry classification are two-class categorical indicators [141], [142]. We start by introducing the following terms:

- True Positives (TP) are correctly classified wet samples;
- False Negatives (FN) are wet samples incorrectly classified as dry;
- True Negatives (TN) are correctly classified dry samples;
- False Positives (FP) are dry samples incorrectly classified as wet.

By consequence:

- $n_{dry} = TP + FP$ is the total number of dry observations;
- $n_{wet} = TP + FN$ is the total number of wet observations;
- $n_{c,dry} = TN + FN$ is the total number of observations classified as dry;
- $n_{c,wet} = TP + FP$ is the total number of observations classified as wet.

KPIS are combinations of the above quantities. A list of relevant KPIS is given in Table II. The table is divided into three parts: the first one shows KPIS computed on the dry observations, the second has KPIS for the wet observations, and the last one has aggregated KPIS over wet and dry observations.

An important aspect to consider when calculating KPIS is the high data imbalance between wet and dry observations, as the occurrence of dry periods is much higher than the one of wet periods. Consequently, metrics, such as the accuracy score $(TP + TN)/(n_{dry} + n_{wet})$, or the error score $(FP + FN)/(n_{dry} + n_{wet})$, which give equal importance to wet and dry observations, bias the evaluation of the performance. The aggregate KPIS proposed in Table II, i.e., Harmonic Mean (HM), Mean Detection Error (MDE) and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), account for this imbalance.

Table III shows the results of some key studies on wet/dry classification. SML studies are based on a few sensors as the SML ground receivers were usually deployed in the framework of ad-hoc experiments. On the other hand, CML research builds from large datasets provided by MNOs and collected from networks of hundreds or thousands of operational links. Results based on smaller CML datasets and not reported in the table are in [143] and [144]. Other wet/dry classification works based on SMLs are in [47] and [68]. The table is structured over eight columns, namely (from left to right): *i*) bibliographical reference; *ii*) OS type (i.e., either CML or SML); *iii*) number of analyzed OS sensors; *iv*) sampling time of OS raw data; *v*) length of the time window where wet/dry labels are assigned (integration time); *vi*) overall observation period; *vii*) measured KPIS; *viii*) notes on ground truth data, thresholds and classification methods used. KPIS in column 7 are calculated over the entire observation window for each sensor and represent median values over the population of OS sensors in the third column. As an exception, in [71] the KPIS were calculated on a daily basis, their median was subsequently computed over a 22-day observation period and the result was eventually averaged over the 26 sensors.

It is not easy to compare the results collected from the above studies, due to the many factors that may affect KPI values, which include: *i*) link characteristics; *ii*) data quantization and sampling; *iii*) data processing; *iv*) integration time; *v*) meteorological conditions and climate of the site where data were collected; *vi*) type of ground truth data; *vii*) validation strategy. Finally, different sets of KPIS are used in different works. However, it is possible to compare KPIS values obtained by different methods over the same dataset or to apply the same method over different datasets.

TABLE III
RELEVANT VALIDATION STUDIES OF WET/DRY CLASSIFICATION BY OSS.

Ref	OS Type	OS Number	Sampling Time	Integration Time	Observation Period	KPIs	Notes
[22]	CML	308	15 min	1 hour	57 days	FAR = .30 Rec = .54 ETS = .42	Ref.: gridded RG data Wet threshold: ref. > 0 mm Method: Statistical
[24]	CML	3904	1 min	1 hour	12 months	MDE = .27 MCC = .47	Ref.: RG-adjusted WR data Wet threshold: ref. > 0.1 mm Method: Statistical
[60]	CML	3904	1 min	1 hour	6 months	Spe ≈ .94 Rec = .62 MCC = .48	Ref.: RG-adjusted WR data Wet threshold: ref. > 0.1 mm Method: statistical
						Spe ≈ .97 Rec = .76 MCC = .69	Ref.: RG-adjusted WR data Wet threshold: ref. > 0.1 mm Method: AI
[71]	SML	26	1 min	5 min	22 rainy days	Spe ≈ .80 Rec > .80 HM ≈ .80	Ref.: WR data Wet threshold: ref. > 0.1 mm h ⁻¹ Method: AI
						Spe < .50 Rec > .95 HM ≈ .60	Ref.: WR data Wet threshold: ref. > 0.1 mm h ⁻¹ Method: statistical
[23]	SML	1	1 min	1 min	34 rain events in 12 months	Rec = .65 FAR = .15	Ref.: Disdrometer data Wet threshold: ref. > 0.1 mm h ⁻¹ Method: statistical

In [24] and [60], the data from 3904 CMLs in Germany are compared with the RADOLAN-RW dataset from the German Weather Service (consisting of RG-adjusted radar products) by resampling the radar gridded data along individual CML paths. In particular, [60] shows that AI methods based on convolutional neural networks are better than statistical methods based on the standard deviation of the RSL, especially in rejecting FNs. Moreover, AI reaches an MCC higher than statistical methods for 95% of CMLs at least. The KPIs in [22] are calculated comparing CML gridded rainfall data, obtained through the RAINLINK open software [51], against operational RG data gridded onto a 5 km × 5 km grid in Emilia-Romagna region (Italy). The relatively low values of recall in [22] are probably due to the comparison being done on gridded products and to the coarse quantization (1 dB) of CML raw data. In fact, both contribute to increase the number of FNs. Aggregate indicators (HM) highlight that AI improves the performance over statistical methods even in the case of SMLs [71]. Please note that in the two studies featuring AI over CML and SML data the recall is similar. On the other hand, the specificity is not comparable due to the different occurrence of dry samples in the two cases (i.e., a continuous six months period in the CML case and only 22 rainy days in the SML case). Finally, [23] is the only study carried out on nearly instantaneously sampled data (i.e., 1-min sampling interval).

B. KPIs for rain intensity retrieval

Several different KPIs are used to assess the capability of CMLs or SMLs to estimate rainfall intensity [15], [21], [24], [56], [85], [145]–[148]. KPIs can be categorized into two types: dimensional KPIs (i.e., those that have units) and dimensionless KPIs (those without units). The first category includes: *i*) Mean Bias Error (MBE); *ii*) Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and bias-corrected RMSE; *iii*) Mean Absolute Error (MAE). The second category includes: *iv*) Relative Bias

(RB); *v*) NMAE; *vi*) Coefficient of Variation (CV); *vii*) Normalized bias-corrected Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE); *viii*) Root Mean Square of relative Error (RMSE_r); *ix*) Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC); *x*) Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE). Although both categories are important, the dimensionless KPIs are particularly advantageous as they enable fair performance comparison across datasets, regions, or in meta-analyses. In this respect, Table IV presents a selected set of dimensionless KPIs, together with the relative formulas and their meaning.

Table V summarizes the results of several relevant studies on the validation of rainfall intensity estimates obtained from CMLs and SMLs. This table has the same layout as previous Table III. The last column reports, among others, the chosen threshold values on rainfall intensity, averaged over the integration time. Intensity values below the threshold are set to zero and discarded from KPI analysis. The first four rows in the table refer to validation studies of CML datasets in the Netherlands, which are also summarized in [147] (their table A.1). CML data in the first three studies are sampled with a 15-min MINMAX strategy, while sampling is instantaneous in the last one (i.e., one sample every 15 min). The comparison of [147] with the version of the dataset in [146] validated with the same procedure, highlights that MINMAX sampling performs quite better than instantaneous sampling over the same 15-min window. Moreover, taking longer integration times improves KPIs. The results for the countrywide network in Germany in [24] are similar as the ones in [147] with a 1-hour integration time, despite a much coarser sampling time in the former case. The work in [56] compares KPIs from two different CML networks across the German-Czech border. A number of gaps and anomalous patterns in data, some of which are specific of one network only, were identified, through extensive data quality control. Despite the different characteristics of the two networks, RB and PCC have similar values. Moreover, the authors show

TABLE IV
MOST SIGNIFICANT DIMENSIONLESS KPIS FOR RAIN INTENSITY RETRIEVAL.

Metric	Formula	Description
Relative Bias (RB)	$\frac{1/N \sum_{i=1}^N (C_i - O_i)}{1/N \sum_{i=1}^N (O_i)}$	It is the average deviation between observed values (O_i), assumed as reference, and calculated (C_i) values, normalized to the mean of the observed values. N is the number of observations. It is often expressed in %. Values near 0 are good scores, negative values indicate underestimation and positive values indicate overestimation.
Normalized Mean Absolute Error (NMAE)	$\frac{1/N \sum_{i=1}^N C_i - O_i }{1/N \sum_{i=1}^N O_i}$	It is the mean absolute error divided by the mean of the observed values. It is often expressed in %. Lower NMAE values indicate better estimates.
Coefficient of Variation (CV)	$\frac{\sqrt{1/(N-1) \sum_{i=1}^N (C_i - O_i)^2}}{1/N \sum_{i=1}^N (O_i)}$	It is the standard deviation of the differences between observed values (O_i), assumed as reference, and calculated (C_i) values, divided by the mean of the observed values. It takes non-negative values. Values close to 0 indicate good scores.
Normalized bias-corrected Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE)	$\frac{\sqrt{1/N \sum_{i=1}^N (C_i - O_i - \text{MBE})^2}}{1/N \sum_{i=1}^N (O_i)}$	Is the normalized quadratic mean of the differences between observed (O_i) and calculated (C_i) values, where it is subtracted the MBE, i.e. the numerator of RB. It is often expressed in %. It is dominated by the largest values, due to the square operation.
Root Mean Square of relative Error (RMSE _r)	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{C_i - O_i}{O_i}\right)^2}$	Is the square root of the mean of the square of the relative errors $(C_i - O_i)/O_i$ between observed (O_i) and calculated (C_i) values. It is dominated by the largest values, due to the square operation.
Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC)	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (O_i - \bar{O})(C_i - \bar{C})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (C_i - \bar{C})^2}}$	It measures the linear relationship between observed (O_i) and calculated (C_i) values. $\bar{O}(\bar{C})$ represents the average of $O_i(C_i)$. It ranges from -1 to +1, where +1 indicates perfect linear correlation between the two datasets. However, a perfect linearity does not imply that the estimator is unbiased.

that the trans-boundary network provides composite rainfall maps able to reproduce the pattern of events as observed by WRs. Finally, the above work highlights large differences in the distribution of KPIS across CMLs. The metrics deteriorate for CMLs with a large value of the minimum detectable rain intensity, due to the combined effect of link characteristics and data quantization, as also highlighted in Section III-C of this review. The analysis in [15] relies on only one available RG for validation. Nonetheless, it is an interesting case study relative to a region (Burkina Faso) where rainfall has different patterns than in Europe and the CML network, located in the urban area of Ouagadougou, is made of relatively low frequency links (10-13 GHz). The authors compare the RG daily accumulation with the one obtained adding-up the 5-min rainfall maps generated through spatial interpolation of CML data. The SML validation works in [23], [75], [149] are based on datasets collected by SmartLNB receivers of the same model in Central Italy. The three sensors used in [149] are the same as in [23] and the observation periods are partially overlapped. In the former case, direct rainfall estimation is carried through AI from SNR data. As with dry/wet classification, KPIS of rainfall intensity highlight an edge of the AI approach over conventional methods based on the power-law expression (6). Another two recent studies based on AI techniques are in [150], [151].

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE TRENDS

We have surveyed the major technical challenges behind the usage of CMLs and SMLs as opportunistic sensors for quantitative rainfall estimates. In both cases, the signature of

precipitation, that is a decrease of the RSL, is contaminated by a number of unwanted disturbances. To mitigate these effects, the general processing chain of the RSL, highlighted in the flowchart of Fig. 1, should also include specific algorithms (at least) for: *i*) identifying and discarding the RSL dips not produced by rain (e.g., due to thermal effects), and *ii*) quantifying the impact of WAA. The latter produces a significant extra signal loss during rainfall, which particularly affects CMLs. Moreover, CMLs and SMLs exhibit intrinsic limitations as rainfall sensors. CMLs are affected by the quantization of the RSL measurements, which limits their sensitivity and accuracy in detecting light rain. For example, a 1 mm/h intensity can be estimated with an accuracy within 25% only by the links operating above 10 GHz if the quantization error is as low as 0.1 dB. Furthermore, the maximum measurable rainfall intensity depends on the sensitivity of microwave receivers. The latter is the RSL threshold value below which the receivers are no longer capable of distinguishing the signal from system noise. In this respect, CMLs, which provide wireless back-hauling in the mobile networks and are based on professional-grade hardware, exhibit a better sensitivity to heavy rainfall than SMLs receivers, usually implemented by low-cost commercial devices.

Validation of rainfall estimates derived from CML or SML data requires a comparison with a ground truth, which is provided by conventional rainfall sensors. Rainfall occurrence (i.e. wet/dry classification), rainfall intensity and rainfall accumulation over a given period are the primary variables analyzed. To this aim, it is necessary to define procedures for associating CML or SML measurements (i.e., a spatial

TABLE V
RELEVANT VALIDATION STUDIES OF RAIN INTENSITY RETRIEVAL BY OSS.

Ref	OS Type	OS Number	Sampling Time	Integration Time	Observation Window	KPIs	Notes
[124]	CML	1751	15 min	15 min	12 rainy days	RB = -13% CV = 1.44 PCC = .66	Ref.: RG-adjusted WR data Threshold: Ref. or CML > 0.1 mm
[146]	CML	3383	15 min	15 min	2.5 years	RB = 1.6% CV = 5.58 PCC = .63	Ref.: RG-adjusted WR data Threshold: None Comparison on gridded data
[146] ^a	CML	3492	15 min	15 min	2.5 years	RB = 5.8% CV = 2.84 PCC = .52	Ref.: RG-adjusted WR data Threshold: Ref. or CML > 0 mm
[147]	CML	1451	15 min	15 min	7 months	RB = 30% CV = 3.70 PCC = .30	Ref.: RG-adjusted WR data Threshold: Ref. or CML > 0 mm
				1 hour		RB = 23% CV = 3.43 PCC = .52	
				1 day		RB = 25% CV = 2.32 PCC = .63	
[24]	CML	3904	1 min	1 hour	12 months	RB = 30% CV = 3.03 PCC = .58	Ref.: RG-adjusted WR data Threshold: Ref. or CML > 0.1 mm
[56]	CML	1167	1 min	1 hour	1 month	RB = -10% PCC = .93	Ref.: RG-adjusted WR data Threshold: Ref. or CML > 0.1 mm German network
		2244				RB = -7% PCC = .86	Ref.: RG-adjusted WR data Threshold: Ref. or CML > 0.1 mm Czech network
[22]	CML	308	15 min	1 hour	57 days	RB = -26% CV = .77 PCC = .68	Ref.: gridded RG data Threshold: Ref. or CML > 0 mm
[15]	CML	259	5 min	1 day	4 months	RB ≈ -10% CV ≈ .55 PCC > .95	Ref.: RG data Threshold: not provided Only CMLs within 3 km from the RG
[21]	SML	37	1 min	10 min	16 rainy days	RMSE _r = 1.6	Ref.: RG data Threshold: Ref. > 0.2 mm
[75]	SML	6	1 min	Event duration	12 months	NMAE = .55 RB = 19%	Ref.: RG data Threshold: Ref. > 1.5 mm
[23]	SML	4	1 min	Event duration	12 months	NMAE = .50 RB = -18%	Ref.: RG data Threshold: Ref. > 0.1 mm h ⁻¹
[149]	SML	3	1 min	Event duration	24 months	NMAE = .11 PCC = .924	Ref.: RG data Threshold: Ref. > 1 mm

^a Reprocessed data as discussed in [147].

average along a straight line) with RG and WR data (i.e. point measurements and 2D maps of rainfall, respectively), set thresholds on the minimum allowable rainfall intensity and choose a set of suitable KPIs. Lists of relevant KPIs for assessing rainfall occurrence and rainfall intensity/accumulation are provided in Tables II and IV, respectively, whereas the results of major validation studies are summarized in Tables III and V, respectively. The calculation of KPIs is influenced by factors such as the different spatial and temporal sampling between OS sensors and ground truth and the high variability of rainfall data. In this respect, temporal sampling adjustments, such as hourly or daily integration, should be used because they mitigate the above effects. Moreover, it emerges that AI techniques outperform conventional methods in detecting rain as well as in quantifying rainfall.

A clear trend in wireless communications is the exploitation of higher frequency bands due to congestion of the lower bands. In 2018, it was reported that most of the almost five million terrestrial wireless links active worldwide operate

below 23 GHz [152]. Today, E-band technology is mature and links in this bandwidth (71-86 GHz) are operational since a few years. E-band links have already been studied for monitoring rainfall as well as water vapor [153]. Finally, even though the D-band (130-174.8 GHz) is still at the level of research, it represents an interesting challenge, due to the availability of large amounts of spectrum. Moreover, rain attenuation at D-band is only marginally higher than at E-band. In satellite communication systems, both broadcasting and broadband services are expected to shift towards the Ka-band [154]. This, in turn, would open up interesting perspectives for opportunistic rainfall sensing, as the increased rain attenuation [155] renders SML-based algorithms much more sensitive [117]. Satellite communications are also pointing towards the use of large and mega constellations of Low-Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites [156], [157]. Obviously, rain attenuation has an impact also on the performance of the down-links of LEO satellite networks, especially those operating in the Ka-band [158]. An analysis of rain effects on LEO ground stations is

presented in [159] for some European locations. In a future perspective, LEO links could help produce 3D tomographic maps of the atmosphere [160].

Future developments in rainfall monitoring include the implementation of synergic data fusion-based networks featuring OSs. For instance, [161] proposes a reconstruction of precipitation fields through a stochastic approach from RG and CML estimates. [132] presents a framework to dynamically generate gridded rainfall fields through an ensemble Kalman filter approach, where data assimilation techniques are used to merge the information from SML observations with forecasts produced by a rainfall advection model. The technique has been validated in both synthetic rain scenarios. In [19], the authors demonstrate the merging of data from WR, personal weather stations, and CMLs into an integrated rainfall product. Finally, in [20], it is shown that a set of gap-filling SML terminals significantly improve the accuracy of 2D rain cell reconstruction gathered from a CML network in a synthetic rain environment.

APPENDIX

A – Total attenuation calculation based on SNR measurements in SML

The k th sample of the SNR from a SML receiver in dry conditions can be written as [44]

$$\bar{\eta}(k) = \frac{\bar{E}_s(k)}{k_B \left[\frac{T_c}{L_{atm}} + T_m \left(1 - \frac{1}{L_{atm}} \right) + T_g + T_r \right]}, \quad (7)$$

where: $\bar{E}_s(k)$ is received energy in dry conditions; k_B is the Boltzmann’s constant; $L_{atm} = 10^{L_z^{(dB)}/(10 \sin \theta)}$ is the attenuation due to atmospheric gases, with $L_z^{(dB)}$ the zenith atmospheric attenuation in dB [91] and θ the satellite elevation above the horizon; T_c , T_m , T_g and T_r are the noise temperatures of microwave cosmic background, meteorological formations, ground, and receiver electronics, respectively. The latter temperature can be obtained from the noise figure $F^{(dB)}$ provided (in dB) by the manufacturer of the LNB, as $T_r = (10^{F^{(dB)}/10} - 1)T_0$, where $T_0 = 290$ K is the customary room temperature.

The rain causes an extra attenuation $A(k)$ in the atmospheric medium with a two-fold effect: i) concerning the numerator, the signal energy is attenuated; ii) concerning the noise spectral density at the denominator, the contribution of the cold extra-terrestrial noise T_c is attenuated, while that of the, definitely hotter, atmospheric noise T_m is increased, thus enhancing the overall noise PSD.

Accordingly, the k th sample of the SNR in wet conditions can be written as [44]

$$\eta(k) = \frac{\bar{E}_s(k)/A(k)}{k_B \left[\frac{T_c}{L_{atm}A(k)} + T_m \left(1 - \frac{1}{L_{atm}A(k)} \right) + T_g + T_r \right]}. \quad (8)$$

Then, by combining (7) and (8), and with some manipulations [44], we eventually get the total rain attenuation as

TABLE VI
TYPICAL VALUES OF SNR PARAMETERS IN SML.

Parameter	Value range
$\bar{\eta}(k)$	8 – 11 dB
T_m	255 – 280 K
T_c	2.78 K
T_g	10 – 50 K
$F^{(dB)}$	0.1 – 1 dB
T_r	6 – 75 K
$L_z^{(dB)}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ dB @ 10 GHz
θ	$> 30^\circ$

$$A(k) = \frac{\bar{\eta}(k)}{\eta(k)} (1 - \xi) + \xi, \quad (9)$$

where we defined $\xi = (T_m - T_c)/[L_{atm}(T_m + T_g + T_r)]$.

Typical values of SNR parameters are listed in Tab. VI.

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